

Correlation of pre-board examination rating and certified public accountant licensure examination performance: An analysis

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the Correlation of the Pre-board Examination Rating and the Certified Public Accountant Licensure Examination Performance. The study determined if the four factors which are curriculum, review facilities, availability of up-to-date materials, and quality teaching affected the pre-board examination. The researchers conducted a survey to gather data from the first-time takers of CPALE in the year 2017 to 2019 students who graduated at St. Dominic College of Asia, Cavite State University- Main Campus, and Imus Institute of Science and Technology. They were selected based on the highest overall performance in the October 2019 CPALE. The study used statistical treatment such as frequency and percentage distribution in analyzing the demographics of the respondents, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) in analyzing the significance of the variables, and the Correlation Analysis for the measurement of the degree of relationship between two variables. Most of the respondents answered that they took the CPALE in 2017 with a pre-board examination rating of 76-80% and 81-85%, while the CPA licensure examination performance rating was 76-80%. Half of the population of the respondents was from Imus Institute of Science and Technology. Out of the four (4) given factors, the curriculum and review facilities were the least rated with regard to the respondent's perception to the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy pre-board examination rating as a basis to improve the licensure examination performance. While availability of up-to-date materials and quality of teaching were the highest indicators that affected the performance in the licensure examination based on the perception of the respondents. It showed that there was no significant relationship between the pre-board examination rating and performance in the CPA licensure examination about the selected factors based on the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). However, the findings showed a correlation coefficient of one for the years 2017, 2018, and 2019 indicating a perfect positive correlation between pre-board examination rating and CPA licensure examination performance. The higher the pre-board examination rating there was a greater possibility in passing the CPA licensure examination. In conclusion, if there was no significant relationship between the given factors regarding the two variables, there may be more factors significantly affecting the two variables since it resulted to a perfect positive correlation. The researchers hereby humbly suggest that future researchers search for more factors that may result to a high significant influence between the pre-board examination rating and CPA licensure examination performance since both variables expresses a perfect positive correlation. Furthermore, proper monitoring, implementation and explanation of changes in the curriculum should also be considered by the school administration and faculty members. Moreover, a yearly evaluation of curriculum should be conducted by the school administration in consultation with the industry representatives, parents and alumni. A small review class size should be maintained to avoid dissatisfaction and discomfort of study environment. The review school and facilities should be based on the performance of the school and the credential of the lecturers.

Keywords: Correlation; Pre-board examination rating; Certified public accountant licensure examination performance.

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Introduction

Many people who enter the accounting sector have the objective of becoming Certified Public Accountants (CPAs) and passing the CPA Licensure Examination is an important accounting career achievement. Employers frequently prefer to recruit accountants who have passed the standardized CPA Licensure Examination or have the ability to pass it because a CPA license is necessary for public accounting and either required or vital for many private and government accounting positions (Shin et al., 2020).

The Professional Regulatory Commission (PRC) offers one of the most challenging government exams, the Certified Public Accountant (CPA) Licensure Examination (Oliva et al., 2017). It was implemented based on Republic Act No. 9298 known as the "Revised Accountancy Law" under the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC), with the main goal to evaluate candidates for the CPA title's general skills and knowledge in addition to determining if they have the necessary technical expertise to be admitted to the profession (Bala, 2008). Bachelor of Science in Accountancy program has prepared graduates with the knowledge and skills to become a public accountant, and to practice, one must obtain a license as a Certified Public Accountant. In other words, the accounting industry has long been associated with the CPA designation (Charron & Lowe, 2009).

It has been part of practice to enroll in CPA review centers to improve the chances of passing the gruesome CPA licensure examinations. To get students ready for upcoming licensure exams issued by the Philippine Regulatory Commission, review centers provide programs or courses of study aimed at updating and enhancing their knowledge, competencies, and abilities after they have already attended in any formal schools.

Before taking the CPA licensure examination, the candidates will undergo series of test as reviewer and preparation for the CPA licensure examination and one of it was the pre-board examination, which was administered by the different review centers. Pre-boards are simulated board exams that are given at the school level. The level of difficulty of the question papers and test format are often on par with those of the real board exams. A mock exam prior to boards may appear useless to some, but its main aim is to allow students to assess their level of preparation and familiarize themselves with board-level question paper. Pre-boards are used to assess how well they performed. The pre-boards can be used by students to monitor their progress. Pre-board exam questions are blueprints for board exams (Chauhan, 2019).

Background of the Study

A philosopher, scientist, and patriot, Benjamin Franklin quoted, “By failing to prepare, you are preparing to fail” – accounting majors fear of. In the records provided by the Philippine Regulation Commission (PRC Board News, 2019) on the Certified Public Accountants Licensure Examination (CPALE) on its previous years, it has shown that 5,468 out of 13,317 with a percentage of 41.06% in October 2015; 5,249 out of 14,390 with a percentage of 36.48% in October 2016; 4,511 out of 14,816 with a percentage of 30.45% in October 2017 and 3,616 out of 14,358 with a percentage of 25.19% in October 2018. The latest CPA licensure examination which was conducted last May and October 2019 showed 1,699 out of 10,319 with a percentage of 16.46% in May and 2,075 out of 14,492 with a percentage of 14.32% in October being the lowest percentage recorded by the Professional Regulatory Commission for the CPA licensure examination results in the last five (5) years.

Generally, a low percentage in CPA Licensure Examination could be viewed favorably in the sense that only those who truly qualified academically are accepted to the profession and therefore can contribute to the improvement of the quality of the service of the practitioners in the profession (Bala, 2008). Graduates typically prepare by participating in a review center, however due to expense concerns and time restraints, few chose to conduct self-review (Orlanda-Ventayen, 2020). In the study of Lascano and Bansiong (2017), it has proven that attendance to review classes can increase one’s chance to hurdle the examination through constant monitoring, evaluation, and feedback. In this case, reviewees take pre-board examination before taking the licensure examination. Students must evaluate their performance on pre-board exams to determine which courses or areas require development and to develop a plan of action in that area (Patelkhana, 2019). The study aims to determine the correlation of pre-board examination ratings to licensure examination performance. Pre-board examinations are an excellent opportunity for students to check their preparation level. Ignoring pre-boards is a huge mistake as they are an excellent opportunity to know where one stands in terms of board exam preparation (Patelkhana, 2019).

A study from Dotado-Maderazo and Ercia (2017) revealed that before completing the board exam, a mock board may be a useful diagnostic tool to determine a graduate’s strengths and weaknesses. Mock boards could provide an overview of the areas where the students’ studies should be concentrated to improve where they appeared to receive a poor score. It helps the graduates acclimate in taking the licensure examination and it can be utilized as a technique to objectively evaluate candidates’ levels of cognitive ability and readiness. In addition to this, the pre-board, sometimes known as a mock board, was effective in educating students. The exam, according to the students, inspired them to study for the national board and introduced them to a test structure that helped them get ready for the Licensure Examination (Dadian et al., 2002).

A study from Pattaguan (2018) claims that availability of wide range or reliable, up-to-date and relevant learning materials contributed to the success in taking the board examination. He claims that broad ranges of resources were positively related to the outcomes and the achievement of the student.

According to a quantitative study from Darling-Hammond (2000), a lecturer’s preparation and certification strongly correlates to the student’s performance. This claim may lead to a set of good characteristics of teachers derived by students from the University of Technology Sydney (n.d.) stating that a good quality of teaching is the manner of teaching in a way which is easy to understand, competent and skillful lecturers that passionate and enthusiastic about what they do and is always organized and prepared for their lessons.

Statement of the Problem

The study aimed to determine the correlation of the Pre-Board Examination Rating and the Certified Public Accountant Licensure Examination results. Specifically, this sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents as to:
 - 1.1. Year Respondents took the CPALE
 - 1.2. Pre-Board Examination Rating
 - 1.3. CPA Licensure Examination Performance
 - 1.4. School Graduated From
2. To what extent do respondents perceive pre-board examination rating as basis to improve board licensure performance, in terms of:
 - 2.1. Curriculum
 - 2.2. Review Facilities
 - 2.3. Availability of up-to-date materials
 - 2.4. Quality of Teaching
3. Is there a significant relationship between the Pre-Board Examination Rating and Performance on the CPA Licensure Examination with regard to variables in no. 2, when grouped according to year graduated?
4. Based on the findings, what are the recommendations to improve licensure examination performance?

Hypotheses

There is no significant relationship between the Pre-Board Examination Ratings and CPA Licensure Examination Performance.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

The study focused mainly on the Correlation of Pre-Board Examination Ratings and CPA Licensure Examination Performance. The collection of data was distributed randomly to Bachelor Science in Accountancy Graduates from three (3) schools with the highest overall performance on the October 2019 CPALE that is St. Dominic College of Asia, Cavite State University – Main Campus and Imus Institute of Science and Technology with a total population of one hundred thirty-nine (139) respondents. The study only covered the graduates who took the CPA Licensure Examination from the year 2017 to 2019. Retakers of the CPA Licensure Examination were excluded in our investigation. Any takers that did not fall as part of the CPA Licensure Exam first takers in the year 2017 to 2019 were not within the scope of the study. The study was done using survey questionnaires.

The study aims to know whether there is a correlation between the Pre-Board Examination Ratings and CPA Licensure Examination Performance. The independent variable will be the pre-board examination rating that the researchers will change to test the dependent variable, CPA licensure examination rating. As it progresses, there will be interventions that will help to know if there is a significant relationship between the two variables, how it affects the students' performance or does it affect students' performance at all. According to Dayaday (2018), the curriculum offers a broad learning experience, and it should be well-explained and monitored by faculty members regarding any modifications. The non-existence of any issues in it is also considered an important aspect for it to contribute in the success of a student. In addition, students from adequate or well-maintained physical facilities which is defined based on the age of the building, lighting, noise, interior color, school size and class size may influence student's academic achievement (Zainuddin & Subri, 2017).

Methods

Research Design

The study used correlational design to distinguish whether a relationship exists between the two variables. Thereof, the study utilized correlational design to determine the significant relationship between the Pre-board Examination Rating and Licensure Examination Performance in the CPA Licensure Examination from year 2017 to 2019 for the data to be more dependable in a time sequence analysis.

The Sample

The researchers selected the CPA licensure examination first time takers of batches 2017 to 2019 as the participants of the study. The population has one-hundred thirty-nine (139) examinees regardless of their gender and age, coming from three (3) schools in Cavite with the highest performances in October 2019 CPALE. St. Dominic College of Asia, Cavite State University - Main Campus, and Imus Institute of Science and Technology. Forty-four (44) examinees were able to answer the survey questionnaire representing 31.7% of the total population. Concerning the objective of the study of finding the correlation of pre-board examination rating into CPA licensure examination performance, only the first-time takers were included.

Sample Procedures

The study used cluster random sampling technique. It is a commonly used technique in a qualitative research for it only selects the subset of a measurable populace in which every individual from the subset has an equivalent likelihood of being picked. Using this kind of sampling is meant to be an unbiased representation of the group. Choosing a sample from a larger population is thought to be a suitable strategy because each member of the population has an equal chance of being selected.

The Instruments

The instrument used to gather the information was a survey questionnaire. The questionnaire is composed of two parts mainly about the profile of the respondents and the perception of the respondents about pre-board examination rating as basis to improve Certified Public Accountant licensure performance.

This indicates to what extent the respondents would agree or disagree to the criteria regarding the given factors. This survey questionnaire was constructed from previous related studies and from other related articles found in the internet to gather information for the present study. The instrument has gone through a test of reliability using Cronbach Alpha, which is a statistic tool, used by researchers to test that the scales applied in their research are fit for their purpose (Taber, 2017). The test showed an alpha (α) of 0.66 indicating that the scales applied in the said instrument is applicable for the research. It was then approved by both the research adviser and the panel. The questionnaire was then distributed via Google forms to randomly selected Certified Public Accountant Licensure Examination first time takers from 2017 to 2019.

Statistical Treatment

Frequency and percentage distribution was applied to specify the percentage of observations that exists according to the profile of the respondents that is useful in expressing the relative percentage of survey responses. Weighted mean was then applied to assign the individual values and testing of the null hypothesis. It was used to calculate the average number in data based on the indicators of the survey. The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is an approach or tool used to analyze the significance of variables in a study. This kind of method is used to identify the influence of a factor or an independent variable by comparing it to dependent variable (Singh, 2018). The ANOVA is computed as $F = \frac{\text{mean sum of squares due to treatment (MST)}}{\text{mean sum of squares due to error (MSE)}}$; where F refers to ANOVA coefficient. The Correlation Analysis was then applied to measure the degree of relationship between two variables and is often measured to count such degree of relationship of the variables (Senthilnathan, 2019).

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

1. Year Respondents took the CPALE

Forty-four (44) respondents answered the survey questionnaire. The year 2017 had the highest frequency of 17 which is equivalent to 38.64% followed by the year 2018, accumulating 34.09% with a frequency of 15. Lastly, for the year 2019 had a percentage of 27.27% with lowest frequency of 12.

2. Pre-Board Examination Rating

In pre-board examination rating, the highest percentage garnering 29.55% were those respondents who answered 76% - 80% and 81% - 85% with a frequency of 13 each. Next is 86% to 90% having a frequency of seven and a percentage of 15.91%. This is followed by 91% to 95% with 13.64% having a frequency of six (6) then followed by 75% and below with five (5) frequency equivalents to 11.36%. Lastly, having 0% at all is 96% to 100%. The data states that a large portion of participants got an average or passing rating in their pre-board exams, which are 76% to 95%, which is somehow good. While there were few respondents who did not pass the pre-board, which were the individuals who got 75% and below considered as failed, and nobody got a rating of 96% to 100%, which is the highest rating.

3. Licensure Examination Performance

The data shown in the licensure examination performance is different from the pre-board examination rating. The rating that got the highest frequency is the 76% to 80% corresponding to 43.18% followed by 81% to 85% having a frequency of 13 (29.55%). Third is the 86% to 90%, with a frequency of three (3) (6.82%). Fourth is the 75% and below labelled as failed got a frequency of nine (9) equivalent to 20.45%.

4. School Graduated

As to school graduated, the highest number of participants came from Imus Institute of Science and Technology representing a frequency of 22 which is equivalent to 50% of the total respondents followed by Cavite State University - Main Campus having 16 respondents which is 36.36%. Lastly, six participants came from St. Dominic College of Asia calculated as 13.64%.

Table 1. Profile of the respondents (n=44)

Demographic Data		Frequency	Percentage
Year took the CPALE	2017	17	38.64%
	2018	15	34.09%
	2019	12	27.27%
Pre-Board Rating	75% and below	5	11.36%
	76% to 80%	13	29.55%
	81% to 85%	13	29.55%
	86% to 90%	7	15.91%
	91% to 95%	6	13.64%
	96% to 100%	0	0.00%
Licensure Rating	75% and below	9	20.45%
	76% to 80%	13	43.18%
	81% to 85%	13	29.55%
	86% to 90%	3	6.82%
	91% to 95%	0	0.00%
	96% to 100%	0	0.00%
School Graduated	Imus Institute of Science and Technology	22	50.00%
	Cavite State University-Indang	16	36.36%
	St. Dominic College of Asia	6	13.64%

Level of Respondents' Pre-Board Examination Rating as Basis to Improve Board Licensure Performance

Table 2 shows the weighted mean and verbal interpretation of the four curriculum factors based on the perception of the respondents when grouped according to the year graduated from 2017-2019. Four curriculum factors are provided on the first part of the survey questionnaire.

The first criteria is the broad learning experience which is based on the current program with lowest weighted mean of 3.75 in the year 2018, while the highest weighted mean of 4.25 for the year 2019. The overall effect has a weighted mean of with a descriptive interpretation of "Agree."

The second criteria on the changes and modification done in the curriculum are well explained by the professor had lowest weighted mean of 3.93 for the year 2018 and the highest weighted mean on of 4.17 for the year 2019. The weighted mean of all the years is 3.93 with a verbal interpretation of "Neutral."

The third criteria, with the lowest weighted mean of 3.75 for the year 2018, and the highest weighted mean came from 2019 with 4.33. The overall weighted mean is 4.07 for the third criteria with a verbal interpretation of "Agree."

The last criteria are the issues and concerns regarding curriculum do not exist in the school or the review school. The lowest weighted mean is from 2018 with a surprising, weighted mean of 2.44 while the highest weighted mean of 3.42 for the year 2019. The overall weighted mean is 3.05, which corresponds to a "Neutral" verbal interpretation.

The overall effect of the four (4) curriculum criteria correspond from year 2017-2019 with the lowest weighted mean of 3.39 for the year 2018 and 2019 having the highest overall weighted mean of 4.04. The total weighted mean of 3.76 among the four (4) criteria and the respondents with a verbal interpretation of "Neutral".

Table 2. Level of respondents' pre-board examination rating in terms of curriculum

Statements	2017	2018	2019	WM
Broad learning experience is based on the current program.	4.06	3.75	4.25	4.00
The changes and modifications done in the curriculum are well-explained by the professors.	4.06	3.63	4.17	3.93
The curriculum is monitored and attended to by the faculty members.	4.19	3.75	4.33	4.07
Issues and concerns regarding curriculum do not exist in the school or the review school.	3.38	2.44	3.42	3.05
Overall Weighted Mean	3.92	3.39	4.04	3.76

Table 3 shows the weighted mean and verbal interpretation of the four review facility factors based on the perception of the respondents when grouped according to the year graduated from 2017-2019. There are four criteria for review facilities shown in Table 3.

The first criteria claims that outside noises dissatisfy students in their classroom and can cause stress. The lowest weighted mean of 3.50 is for the year 2018 while the year 2019 shows the highest weighted mean of 4.08. It shows an overall weighted mean of 3.75 with a verbal interpretation of "Neutral."

The second criteria regarding the industrial setting and color gave impact on students on their performance in school has the lowest weighted mean in 2018 with 3.19 and the highest weighted mean came from the year 2017 with 3.56. It indicates an overall weighted mean for the second criteria of 3.41 making a verbal interpretation of "Neutral."

The third criteria claims that the small size of school reduces negative behavior of students, improve positive attitude and achievement. It shows the lowest weighted mean in the year 2018 with 2.81 and highest weighted mean in 2019 with 3.42 having an overall weighted mean of 3.11 with an interpretation of "Neutral."

The last criteria relating to the small review class giving positive factors on the academic outcomes or achievement had the lowest weighted mean in the year 2019 of 3.33 and highest weighted mean in the year 2017 with 3.81. Lastly, 3.59 is the total weighted mean for the last criteria with a verbal interpretation of "Neutral."

The overall weighted mean of the review facilities factors related to the years 2017-2019 had the lowest weighted mean in the year 2018 of 3.27 and both 2017 and 2019 having 3.58 as the highest weighted mean. The effect of weighted mean is 3.47 for the four (4) criteria under review facilities with a verbal interpretation of "Neutral."

Table 3. Level of respondents' pre-board examination rating in terms of review materials

Statements	2017	2018	2019	WM
Outside noise dissatisfies student in their classroom and cause stress.	3.75	3.50	4.08	3.75
Industrial setting and color gave impact on students their performance in school.	3.56	3.19	3.50	3.41
Small size of school reduces negative behavior of student and improves positive attitude and achievement.	3.19	2.81	3.42	3.11
Small review class size can give positive factors on the academic outcomes or achievement.	3.81	3.56	3.33	3.59
Overall Weighted Mean	3.58	3.27	3.58	3.47

The first criteria in line with the availability of up-to-date materials, which is investing on and reviewer books and those recommended by the professors, shows a result of highest mark on 2019 with a 4.92 weighted mean and the lowest in 2017 with a mark of 4.56. The average weighted mean of this criterion is 4.70 with a verbal interpretation of "Agree".

The second criteria which discusses that reading theories and answering problems and applying these to understand it fully, shows a result of highest weighted mean of 4.92 in the year 2019 and lowest mark on the year 2017 with a weighted mean of 4.69. Thus, results to an average weighted mean of 4.77 with a verbal interpretation of "Agree".

The third criteria that focuses on finding the updated library book, e-books, and other textbooks easily, shows a result with the highest weighted mean of 4.38 in 2017 and the lowest in 2018 with a weighted mean of 3.88. These results to an average weighted mean of 4.09, which is verbally interpreted as "Agree".

The last criteria, which are collecting all available books from different authors on a given subject, have the highest result in 2019 with a weighted mean of 4.33 and the lowest result on 2018 with 3.88 weighted mean. This gives an average result of 4.23 that is verbally interpreted as "Agree".

The overall weighted mean of four (4) criteria under the factor of Availability of up-to-date books, shows a close result of 4.47 in 2017 as the highest record and the lowest of 4.04 in the year 2019. Thus, result to an overall average weighted mean of 4.45 that is verbally interpreted as "Agree".

Table 4. Level of respondents' pre-board examination rating in terms of availability of up-to-date materials

Statements	2017	2018	2019	WM
Investing on the reviewer books and recommended textbooks of the professors.	4.56	4.69	4.92	4.70
Reading theories and answering as many problems as possible; Applying and understanding the theories.	4.69	4.75	4.92	4.77
Updated library books, e-books, and other textbooks are easy to find.	4.38	3.88	4.33	4.09
Collecting all available textbooks from different authors for a given subject for more references.	4.25	3.88	4.33	4.23
Overall Weighted Mean	4.47	4.30	4.04	4.45

The first criteria under the quality of teaching, focusing on how clearly do lecturers explained and helped the students to understand, presents a result of 4.75 weighted mean in 2019, which is the highest record, and 4.44 in 2017 as the lowest.

This results to an average weighted mean of 4.61 that has a verbal interpretation of "Agree". The second criteria are that the lecturers were competent, knowledgeable, and up to date in their subject area. This had a very close result of 4.81 in 2018, which was considered the highest weighted mean and the lowest in 2017 & 2019 with the same result of 4.75. This close records result to an average weighted mean of 4.77, which is considered "Agree" when verbally interpreted.

The third criteria, which focuses on the enthusiasm of the lecturers when coming to their class, shows the highest result of 4.67 weighted mean in 2019 and recorded the lowest in 2018 with a weighted mean of 4.38. The average weighted mean recorded under this criterion is 4.52 with a verbal interpretation of "Agree".

The last criteria, that the lecturers were well prepared and structured their lecture content effectively, presents the highest weighted mean in 2019 with 4.83 and the lowest in 2017 with 4.69 weighted mean. This results to an average weighted mean of 4.75 that is verbally interpreted as "Agree".

The overall weighted mean of all four (4) criteria under the quality of teaching, shows a relatively close result between the highest and the lowest. The highest overall weighted mean shows a record of 4.75 and the lowest have 4.61. This close record of the overall weighted mean results to an overall average weighted mean of 4.66 that has a verbal interpretation of "Agree".

Table 5. Level of respondents' pre-board examination rating in terms of quality of teaching

Statements	2017	2018	2019	WM
Lecturers explained in a way which was clear and helped students to understand.	4.44	4.69	4.75	4.61
Lecturers were highly competent, knowledgeable, and up-to-date in their subject area.	4.75	4.81	4.75	4.77
Lecturers come into class full of enthusiasm for their subject, professional area, and teaching role.	4.56	4.38	4.67	4.52
Lecturers were well-prepared and structured their lecture content effectively.	4.69	4.75	4.83	4.75
Overall Weighted Mean	4.61	4.66	4.75	4.66

Significant Relationship Between the Pre-Board Examination Rating and Performance on the Licensure Examination When Grouped According to Year Graduated

Table 6. ANOVA computation of 2017 to 2019

Year	Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
2017	Between Groups	57.340	15	3.823	5.945	0.000	1.708
	Within Groups	154.313	240	0.643			
	Total	211.652	255				
2018	Between Groups	127.496	15	8.500	12.066	0.000	1.708
	Within Groups	169.063	240	0.704			
	Total	296.559	255				
2019	Between Groups	57.583	15	3.839	6.237	0.000	1.724
	Within Groups	108.333	176	0.616			
	Total	165.917	191				

Table 6 shows the significant influence of each given factor according to the year the examinees took the Certified Public Accountant Licensure Examination from 2017 to 2019. Using the analysis of variance (ANOVA) test at a significance level of (α) 0.05, the F is 5.95 was greater than the f-critical value of 1.708 in 2017. In 2018, the F was still greater than the f-critical with values of 12.07 and 1.71, respectively while F is 6.24 and f-critical is 1.72, which was still lower than F in the year 2019. Overall, this indicates that the following factors do not have significant influence on the pre-board examination rating and performance in the CPA licensure examination.

Table 7. Correlation of Pre-Board Examination Rating and CPA Licensure Examination Performance

Variables	2017	2018	2019
Pre-board Rating	82.94	82.50	83.33
Licensure Examination Performance	79.94	79.13	79.58
Correlation Coefficient			
2017	1		
2018	1	1	
2019	1	1	1

In Table 7, the correlation coefficient of one indicates a perfect positive correlation of the pre-board examination rating and the CPA licensure examination performance from 2017 to 2019. It shows that when the pre-board examination rating increases, the CPA licensure examination performance increases or the opposite. It indicates that there is a direct relationship between the two variables, and they move in the same direction. The findings supported the study from India Today Web Desk (2018) that pre-board examination rating is essential to the student in taking the board examination. However, it contrasts a statement from the same source, as the pre-board examination rating can be a strong indicator of licensure examination performance.

Conclusions

The overall purpose of the study was to determine the Correlation of the Pre-Board Examination Rating and Certified Public Accountant Licensure Examination Performance and how it can be a basis to improve the Certified Public Accountant Licensure Examination. Most of the respondents were the individuals who took the Certified Public Accountant Licensure Examination in the year 2017. Majority of the respondents had a rating of 76-80% and 81-85% in their Pre-Board Examination Rating. CPA Licensure Examination Performance. Most of the respondents had a rating of 76-80% in the CPA Licensure Examination. Majority of the respondents graduated from Imus Institute of Science and Technology.

Since the overall weighted mean of the curriculum is 3.76 with an interpretation of "Neutral," It can be concluded that the curriculum has an average influence in the perception of the respondents of the pre-board examination rating as basis to improve licensure examination performance.

The overall weighted mean of the review facilities is 3.47 with an interpretation of "Neutral." It can be concluded that the review facilities has an average influence in the perception of the respondents of the pre-board examination rating as basis to improve licensure examination performance.

The overall weighted mean for the updated materials is 4.45 indicating an interpretation of "Agree" from the respondents. It can be concluded that the availability of up-to-date materials has a definite influence in the perception of the respondents regarding the pre-board examination rating as basis to improve licensure examination performance.

Lastly, the quality of teaching has an overall weighted mean of 4.66, which is the highest weighted mean among four factors indicating an interpretation of "Agree." It can be concluded that the quality of teaching has a definite influence in the perception of the respondents regarding the pre-board examination rating as basis to improve licensure examination performance.

Out of the four (4) given factors, the curriculum and review facilities are the factors that were the least rated with regard to the respondent's perception to the pre-board examination rating as a basis to improve the licensure examination performance while availability of up-to-date materials and quality of teaching were the highest indicators that these factors affected the performance in the licensure examination based on the perception of the respondents.

According to the year graduated, the given factors: Curriculum, Review Facilities, Availability of Up-To-Date Materials, and Quality of Teaching resulted to no significant relationship between the Pre-Board Examination Rating and Performance on the Licensure Examination. However, it was then followed by the correlation coefficient of 1 indicating that both variables have a perfect positive correlation from years 2017-2019. The higher the pre-board examination rating there is a greater possibility in passing the CPA licensure examination. In conclusion, if there is no significant relationship between the given factors regarding the two variables, there may be more factors significantly affecting the two variables since it resulted to a perfect positive correlation.

Recommendations

Based on the results, both availability of up-to-date materials and quality of teaching have the strongest relevance in regard to the improvement of passing the Certified Public Accountant Licensure Examination while curriculum and review facilities appear to be the least relevant in view thereof, the researchers hereby suggest the following:

- Proper monitoring, implementation and explanation of changes in the curriculum. It should also be considered by the school administration and faculty members. Moreover, a yearly evaluation of curriculum should be conducted by the school administration in consultation with the industry representatives, parents and alumni.
- A small review class size should be maintained to avoid dissatisfaction and discomfort of study environment. The review school and facilities should be based on the performance of the school and the credential of the lecturers.

Moreover, future researchers are encouraged to search for more factors that may result to a high significant influence between the pre-board examination rating and CPA licensure examination performance since both variables expresses a perfect positive correlation.

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